

Migration and Its Discontents: A Critical Study of Global Movement and Its Drivers

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Abstract

Over the past years, various attempts have been made by government to stop excessive migration of Nigerians to other countries, in search of greener pastures. Unfortunately, nothing seems to materialize, and Nigerians are still leaving the shores of the country. In view of this, this study hopes to provide its readers with the necessary information needed to understand the social and economic problems migration has on the country, in addition, the study hopes to be useful to the government and public policy makers so as to seek out best measures to tackle political corruption and unemployment, which are reasons why Nigerians leave the country, in most cases permanently, in search of better jobs, and living conditions. It is hoped that the study will be useful for future researchers in the area of discourse.

Introduction

Since the beginning of creation, humans have always involved themselves in movement activities. This has been a major feature in the history of Nigeria and the entire globe generally (Akanji, 2015). Migration cannot be inevitable from the history of the story of man, families, villages and nation-state. Therefore, migration can be traced as far back as the existence of man most especially when man desired to go in search of food during various famine seasons; also, another reason for migrating in those days was the desire of separating from the crowd as well as the seeking for independence (Jones, 2016). As earlier revealed virtually all individuals and nations states have one or two traces of migration history (internal and international) mostly influenced by two factors these are the “Pull” and “Push” factors. Migration can be internal or international. Internal migration explains the movement of individuals within same geographical territory which in this case can be from rural to urban or from Lagos to Abuja. While, international migration has to do with the crossing of borders or international boundaries such as Cameroon to Nigeria described as south-south migration, Nigeria to United States of America described also as south north migration (Derek, 2016). Although a small number of Nigerians have always migrated to neighboring West African countries and overseas since the 1960s, it was not until the mid-1970s that Nigeria experienced the mass migration of its nationals abroad. Besides Ghana and Benin, the main destinations of Nigerians migrants include the United States, Canada, and western European countries, particularly the United

Kingdom, Germany, Holland and Italy (Asiedu 2015; Anarfi et al 2018; Twum Baah 2015; Manuh et al 2016). These migrants included highly skilled professionals such as lecturers, teachers, accountant, doctors, and nurses as well as unskilled workers including masons, carpenters, drivers, tailors, watchmen, cooks, etc. (Die, 2017; Asiedu 2016). By the mid-1990s the number of Nigerians abroad was estimated at more than three million persons, constituting about 10-20 percent of the population (Anarfi et al 2016; Piel 2015). As a result, the development of the “Nigerians diaspora” began to take shape (Awumbila, et al 2017; Munuh, 2015; Nieswand, 2017; Tonah, 2016). The movement of these migrants since early 1990 has been attributed to the unstable political conditions, decline in the economy in Nigeria and poor living conditions (Awumbbila et al 2017). While new migrants continue to leave Nigeria in search of greener pastures abroad, an increasing number of Nigerians who migrated abroad most especially to Libya have been returning home. However, less attention is given to how these migrants survived on their return. It is against this backdrop that the study will examine the role of the national commission for refugees, migrants and reintegrating returnees into the Nigerian society.

Understanding Migration: Definition and Types

Definition Migration?

Migration is an integral part of human history. Human beings have been moving from place to place for social, economic, or political reasons from their earliest days (Koser 2016). Broadly, migration is usually explained in terms of time and space. It is defined as the movement of people that involves a change in usual residence across an administrative boundary such as a village, town, district, or country (Kok 1999). Migration can be in the form of immigration, which is described as the number of people entering a receiving area, or emigration, which refers to the flow of people from a country over a given period of time. Moreover, there are two types of migration: internal, when migrants move within their country; and international migration, a situation in which migrants live outside of their country of birth for at least one year (Poulain and Perrin 2001). Skeldon (2017, p. 2) argued that migration in general, and international migration in particular, is a complicated concept because “its measurement depends entirely upon how it is defined in time and across space”. However, the International Organization for Migration (IOM) has provided a better definition of international migration or a “migrant” by avoiding time and territorial limitations. A migrant is any person who is moving or has moved across an international border or within a State away from his/her habitual place of residence, regardless of (1) the person’s legal status; (2) whether the movement is voluntary or involuntary; (3) what the causes for the movement are; or (4) what the length of the stay is (IOM 2019). The above definition to some extent considers the multifaceted nature of the concept of migration. However, the question is not only related to the length of time individuals should reside or the distance they should travel to be recognised as migrants, but it is also connected to their long-term status after receiving citizenship in their

host country. It is important to ask what would happen after they obtain their new citizenship: would they continue to be migrants, the host countries' citizens, or both? In addition, Koser (2016) stated that defining a migrant as "someone living outside their own country for a year or more" does not provide a complete answer to the question "who is a migrant?" for various reasons:

First, the concept "migrant" covers a wide range of people in a wide variety of situations. Second, it is very hard to count migrants and to determine how long they have been abroad. Third, just as important as defining when a person becomes a migrant is to define when they stop being a migrant. Finally, it has been suggested that, as a result of globalisation, there are now new "types" of migrants with new characteristics, for example, comprising transnational communities or diaspora (Koser 2016, p. 14). The term "migrant" comprises a wide range of people, including those who are forced into exile, and this connects to the idea that people migrate voluntarily or involuntarily for socio-economic and political reasons (Bauman 1996; Kempf 2006; Batista-Pinto Wiese 2010). Some people migrate voluntarily—these are referred to as "Tourists" in Bauman's (1996) terms. Nevertheless, many are forced to leave their country due to war, persecution, and extreme economic hardships in their home countries (UNHCR 2018b). The UNHCR (2018b) further stated that such migrants carry out dangerous border crossings and experience extreme displacement and hardship in transit countries. Yet, the world is not hospitable to forced migrants or, in Bauman's terms, the "Vagabonds" (Bauman 1996). They can be victims of xenophobic violence (Misago 2016) and strict immigration control, including detention and even deportation (Kritzman-Amir and Shumacher 2012). Furthermore, migrants are categorised according to different labels based on the cause and destination of their movement and their legal status in their country of destination. Accordingly, the term "migrant" encompasses displaced people: "individuals who are forced to move against their will" (Shamsuddoha et al. 2012, p. 18). People are also classed as internally or externally displaced depending on whether they crossed their countries' borders or not. Internally displaced people flee their homes, but they remain within their country of origin. They might receive a supply of relief materials such as food, medicines, and other basic facilities, but they are not entitled to refugee status under the UN convention (International Committee of the Red Cross 2010). Refugees often cross international borders due to a lack of protection from their government. The 1951 Geneva Convention highlights the distinctive features of refugees. A person who is outside his or her country of nationality or habitual residence; has a well-founded fear of being persecuted because of his or her race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion; and is unable or unwilling to avail him or herself of the protection of that country, or to return there, for fear of persecution (UNHCR 2011, p. 3).

Thus, the broad concept of migration includes refugees, who are externally displaced people, and other individuals who move from one place to another for socio-economic and political reasons. However, it is important to note that not all migrants are refugees. As can be understood from the above definition, refugees face a threat of persecution and lack the protection of their own country. In contrast, non-refugee migrants usually leave their country for employment, family reunification, or study, and enjoy their governments' protection even when they are abroad. Based on the Geneva Convention, many countries have set eligibility criteria for determining the refugee status of individuals. For example, the Home Office (2016) states that individuals must satisfy two requirements to stay in the UK as refugees. First, they must be unable to live safely in any part of their own country due to racial, religious, and political persecution and other human rights violations. Second, they must have failed to obtain protection from their government. Therefore, anyone without one or more of these features is not recognised as a refugee. In such cases, countries recognise these migrants as asylum seekers, pending acceptance or rejection of their international protection. Asylum seekers are individuals who are seeking international protection in other countries but have not yet received any legal recognition or status (Phillips 2011).

Reasons for Migration:

The causes for migration can be classified as “economic migration, social migration, political migration, and environmental migration” and the factors for migration can be summed up or called summation of various “Push (reason to leave the area)” and “Pull (reasons to move to the area)” factors. The generally identified classification for causes of migration are:

- **Economic Migration** refers to migrating for career growth or for job search.
- **Social Migration** refers to relocating in search of better life quality or to be near to family and relatives.
- **Political Migration** is in situations where the person is willing to escape adverse scenarios like war or political persecution.
- **Environmental Migrations** are done in situations of natural disasters.

Causes of Migration

Some individuals relocate in pursuit of employment or economic prospects, to reunite with family, or to pursue education. Others move to escape conflict, persecution, or significant human rights abuses. Additionally, some people are driven to move due to the negative impacts of climate change, natural disasters, or other environmental factors.

1. For Education purposes

Education is one of the primary economic reasons for migration. The recent stats that highlight this cause of migration are:

2: For Career Enhancement

Yet other economic reasons for migration is seeking better career prospects.

3. Overpopulation

Overpopulation is another economic reason for migration, affecting growth and better career prospects.

4. Religious or Social Reasons

The social reasons for migration is also one of the major considered factor.

5. Poverty

Poverty is one of the major factors badly affecting the Indian economy and a main reason for migration. It is a condition where an individual household is not even able to meet basic living requirements. It can be a result of various reasons like low wages, constant increases in prices, unemployment, lack of awareness, etc.

Better Healthcare

Health care is the fundamental right of every individual. Even though the technological advancement that India witnessed, people are willing to go abroad for better healthcare services.

- The Economic Times reports that as of 2021, there was a 20% increase in visa queries, with respect to the individuals willing to move abroad to attain better and safer health care services.
- The queries were not just for the USA, Canada, and Australia but also for less popular countries like New Zealand, Germany, the UK, etc., as well.

Political causes

Policies and country stability are other major reasons for migration as individuals seek safety and well-being.

- The migrants under this cause are the ones who are in search to experience political freedom compared to the restrictive lives back in their origin countries.
- Political push factors that are influencers are persecutions based on political identification, policy changes, or civil wars.
- For example, the recent Agriculture Policy changes made in India are believed to negatively impact with respect to the cultivators, resulting in a change of livelihood. Sri Lanka is one of the best examples of the political and economic crisis of 2022.

War or Conflict Zones

War is one of the rare factors, which only includes push factors of migration. It is typically the scenario where the individual does not have much of a choice, rather to move or migrate and, most of the time, become a refugee.

- This is a situation where the choices, aspirations, and willingness of individuals do not have a role and the sole focus is to make it a place to secure lives.

- The recent Ukraine and Russia war has shown us how adversely wars affect the lives and livelihood of people not only in the war countries but as well have a huge impact on the other countries having business or dependencies with them.

Environmental factors

The environment has always been a driving factor for migrators; these include natural disasters like floods, droughts, earthquakes, climate changes, etc.

- The International Organization for Migration defines environmental migrants as the ones who are obliged to leave their origins or home as a result of sudden or progressive environmental changes or conditions, as it has caused a major affect to their living conditions and lives. This movement could be temporarily or permanently, to internal (within the country) or international (abroad) migration.
- The estimates for these migrants are quite difficult. However, IOM states that the numbers could reach 1 billion by the end of 2050.

Methodology

Study Design

A research design means the entire procedure employed to bring together different components of a study in a lucid and logical way, thereby making sure that the research problem is handled adequately. The design carries the blueprint for the collection, measurement and dissection of data. For this reason, the study adopts the survey design. The imperative of this design is to interrogate respondents on the topic of discourse and then analyse their responses. This is done through the use of questionnaire.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is centred on displaced persons, returnees in camps in Mbiama, Akinima, Akiniso and Abua of Rivers State.

Sources of Data

The data used for the study are from two sources: the primary and secondary. The primary sources are; questionnaire and interviews, while for that of the secondary sources are; government journals, articles, the internet, etc.

Sample Size

A sample is a subset of a population that is used to represent the entire population. In doing a research, it is practically not feasible to survey every member of the study population because it can create ambiguity and obscure the objectivity of the study, given the large number of the population. In order to avoid these things, the researcher chooses a smaller number of respondents. If the sample chosen truly represents the larger group, the researcher can draw a generalisation. In view of this, the study will use 100 respondents out of the entire population in the study area. These 100 respondents are internally displaced persons, returnees living in camps in Mbiama, Akinima, Abuoha, Akiniso. It is believed that the views of these 100 respondents will represent the general view of the people in camps since everyone cannot be sampled.

Sampling Technique

A sampling technique is used in drawing samples from a population usually in a way that the sample will facilitate and accommodate the general view of the population on a particular topic. A sample technique is a pattern used in determining samples vital for particular studies. In Social Science researches, there are two types of sampling techniques: probability and non-probability sampling techniques. The probability sampling technique uses randomization to select sample members. This type of sampling technique allows every member of the study population to have an equal chance of participating in the study. The non-probability sampling technique uses non-random technique. This type is basically reliant on the judgement of the researcher, and it is restricted to individuals the researcher decides to include in the study. There are subsets of the probability sampling, and they are: Simple Random Sampling (SRS), stratified sampling, cluster sampling, systematic sampling and multistage sampling. For the non-probability sampling, the subsets are: convenience sampling, haphazard sampling, purposive sampling, quota sampling, snowball sampling, etc. For this study, the simple random sampling technique is ideal since it deals with randomization of respondents in an independent and all-inclusive way. The sampling frame form consists of community leaders, youths, students and business people from which the respondents will be randomly selected.

Methods of Data Collection

Data collected for this study are from questionnaire, interviews, the internet and articles. These methods provided invaluable information for the researcher.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected are analyzed in line with the research objectives. These responses collected from the respondents are measured in frequency and percentage tables.

Data Presentation

Demographic Features of Respondents

Table 1: Age of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-28	86	47.8
29-38	64	35.5
39-Above	30	16.7
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 1 on age of respondents, 18-28 years accounted for 86(47.8%), 29-38 years accounted for 64(35.5%), 39 years and above accounted for 30(16.7%) of respondents used for the study.

Table 2: Sex of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	72	40
Female	108	60
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From the table above, on the sex of respondents, accounted for 72(40%), female accounted for 108(60%) of respondents used for the study.

Data Analysis

Table 3: Political instability is a reason for international migration?

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	86	47.8
Agree	58	32.2
Strongly disagree	26	14.4
Disagree	10	5.5
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 3 on political instability as a reason for international migration, strongly agree accounted for 86(47.8%), agree accounted for 58(32.2%), strongly disagree accounted for 26(14.4%), disagree accounted for 10(5.5%) of respondents that answered the question.

Table 4: High rate of terrorism and insecurity is a reason for international migration?

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	83	46.1
Agree	61	33.9
Strongly disagree	23	12.8
Disagree	13	7.2
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 4. on the high rate of terrorism and insecurity as a reason for international migration, strongly agree accounted for 83(46.1%), agree accounted for 61(33.9%), strongly disagree accounted for 23(12.8%), disagree accounted for 13(7.2%) of respondents that answered the question.

Table 5: Lack of employment opportunities is a reason for international migration?

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	88	48.9
Agree	59	32.8
Strongly disagree	21	11.7
Disagree	12	6.6
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 5 on lack of employment opportunities as a reason for international migration, strongly agree accounted for 88(48.9%), agree accounted for 59(32.8%), strongly disagree accounted for 21(11.7%), disagree accounted for 12(6.6%) of respondents that answered the question.

Table 6: Low standard of living is a reason for international migration?

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	91	50.5
Agree	56	31.1
Strongly disagree	26	14.4
Disagree	10	5.5
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 6 on low standard of living as a reason for international migration, strongly agree accounted for 91(50.5%), agree accounted 56(31.1%), strongly disagree accounted for 26(14.4%), disagree accounted for 7(3.9%) of respondents that answered the question.

Discussion of Findings

One of the problems bedeviling Nigeria at the moment is the forced migration of her citizens to other countries. This was not the case over five decades ago. The deteriorating situation in the country has created fertile grounds for Nigerians to leave at all cost. In the course of conducting this research, some factors or reasons were discovered as to why Nigerians leave the country. One of the reasons is the political instability in Nigeria. Politics is supposed to engender development in any society, but that is not the case in Nigeria, as politics has created violent crimes against humanity. The Boko Haram menace in the North-East has some political undertone, and the group has rendered many homeless; others have fled the North-East for safety in other countries. The study also discovered that the political leaders are insensitive to the plights of the victims. Another reason for the migration of Nigerians to other countries is lack of employment opportunities. A country as Nigeria, with much resources to generate employment effortlessly, is struggling to deal with the problem of unemployment that increases daily. Graduates leave school with no hope of being gainfully employed. Many become frustrated, and run to nearby countries like Libya, Ghana, South Africa in search of jobs that are payable adequately.

Summary and Conclusion

The ultimate desire of every returnee into Nigeria is to relocate back to him or her community of origin, pick up the broken pieces of their lives and rebuild their means of livelihood. As Nigeria intensifies the battle against insecurity, unemployment and poor standard of living, agencies were created to help returnees fully incorporate into their own country they left due to insecurity, unemployment and poor living conditions. Consequently, the National Commission For Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons was created. The body was tasked with the responsibility of assisting returnees settle in. the body was to help returnees in the provision of food and shelter psychological and social support. Sadly, the NCFRMI has not been able to totally perform its functions. The body is challenged by poor funding. This is because the government has so much to cater for, and it is taking a toll on the function of the NCFRMI.

Recommendations

- (i) There is the need for the Federal Government of Nigeria to have a stricter control of border posts in northern Nigeria so as to avert illegal immigrants from the Maghreh region into the country. This would require the establishment of joint border patrol between Nigeria, Chad, Niger, Cameroon and Benin republics using heavy surveillance equipment like well equipped helicopters and satellites.

- (ii) A strategic collaboration between Government, Non State Actors and Private Sectors in addressing the menace is a strategic step that needs to be taken to sustain these process there needs to be grassroots participation and knowledge to ensure parents and siblings alike know the dangers of these unhealthy adventures such as illegal migration.
- (iii) The Federal Government should undertake intensive policing of the country's border especially the Nigeria – Chad and Nigeria - Cameroon borders in the north eastern region of the country. This measure will prevent the insurgents and their foreign supporters from entering or establishing camps within the country's borders.
- (iv) The Federal Government of Nigeria should enlist the support of citizens in the fight against the insurgents by information anyone who gives reasonable information to security organizations about the members of the group. Government should also ensure that such persons are protected against insurgent's reprisal attacks.

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